

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE NAMES OF ANIMALS AND BIRDS WITH TURKIC LANGUAGES USED IN THE LANGUAGE OF AHMADI'S MASNAVI "JAMSHID AND KHURSHID"

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Abstract

The Azerbaijani literary language was used as the language of poetry by many poets who brought up in Eastern Anatolia at the end of the 13th century and the 14th century, and the poems written in this language were almost the first examples of the Ottoman Turkish literary language. Because we do not have material evidence that written literature in Anatolia began before the 13th century. Ahmadi is one of the successors of Anatolian Turkish Islamic literature, which started with Mevlana Jalaladdin Rumi and Yunis Amre in the 13th century, and is one of the greatest poets of the 14th century. Ahmadi, one of the founders of classical Turkish poetry, in his works written in 14th century Anatolian Turkish, gave the first examples of the written and literary language of Anatolian Beyliks and Ottoman period Turkish, and made great contributions to the use of the Turkish language not only as a written and literary language, but also as a scientific language. Considering that Ahmadi, one of the greatest poets of the 14th century, on the one hand witnessed the disintegration of the Seljuk Empire, on the other hand, the emergence of various beyliks in Anatolia and the laying of the foundations of the Ottoman Empire, we can say that the poet's works written in Turkish had an unparalleled impact on the development of Oghuz Turkic. In the article, the names of animals and birds used in the language of Ahmadi's masnavi "Jamshid and Khurshid" have been selected and included in the research, divided into groups and compared with the language of old and medieval Turkic monuments, as well as the forms of development in modern Turkic languages.

Keywords: Oghuz Turkic, Old Anatolian Turkish, Middle Ages, Tajeddin Ahmadi, Jamshid and Khurshid, animal names, Turkic languages.

INTRODUCTION

Linguistic monuments occupy an important place among the spiritual wealth of humanity, as well as immortal samples of world culture. Turkish-language monuments are also very important sources in terms of reflecting the rich linguistic history, national way of thinking of the old Turkish nation. Our primary native-language monuments, literary-fictional language samples, created in the 13th-15th centuries, appeared mainly in Eastern Anatolia, in the areas bordering Eastern Anatolia. For many centuries, Azerbaijani Turks have chosen Eastern Anatolia as their homeland and have become the rooted population of this ancient land. Therefore, it is not the right step to evaluate the works written in Eastern Anatolia and the territories bordering on Eastern Anatolia in the 13th-14th centuries separately from Azerbaijani linguistics and literary studies, and to ignore the existence of these works [14, p.381]. In the words of Fuad Koprulu, Eastern Anatolia is an area dominated by the Azerbaijani dialect. He still wrote in the 20s that: "Basically, there is no difference between the old and primitive form of the Seljuk-Ottoman dialect and the Azerbaijani dialect" [16, p.6]. In the second half of the 14th century, powerful wordsmiths such as Gazi Burhaneddin, Erzurumlu Darir, who made a name for themselves in the literary environment of their time, lived and created in Eastern Anatolia. The Azerbaijani literary language was used as the language of poetry by many poets who brought up in Eastern Anatolia at the end of the 13th century and the 14th century, and the poems written in this language were almost the first examples of the Ottoman Turkish literary language. Because we do not have material evidence that written literature in Anatolia began before the 13th century.

Ahmadi is one of the successors of Anatolian Turkish Islamic literature, which started with Mevlana Jalaladdin Rumi and Yunis Amre in the 13th century, and is one of the greatest poets of the 14th century. Considering that the era in which Ahmadi lived coincided with the disintegration of the Seljuk Empire, the emergence of various beyliks in Anatolia, and the laying of the foundations of the Ottoman Empire, we can say that the works written by the poet in Turkish had an unparalleled impact on the use and development of the Turkic language of science and literature of the time. As we know Ahmadi, is a valuable poet who lived in the period of the beyliks, which were the continuation of the Anatolian Seljuk state, and was first under the patronage of the Germiyan Beylik and then the Ottomans. Mehmet Fuat Koprulu by excluding Nasimi and called Ahmadi the greatest poet of the 14th century. Ahmadi is a personality who produced the most works of the 14th century and had a great role in the construction of classical literature. Ahmedi, who produced numerous and voluminous works, is a great poet as well as a master of his time and a powerful artist who uses the Turkish language beautifully. In his qasidas and ghazals in his "Divan", Ahmadi showed the arts of the Iranian school of poetry, as well as reflected the intricacies of the Turkish soul and the expressive power of the Turkish language.

Ahmadi, one of the founders of classical Turkish poetry, in his works written in 14th century Anatolian Turkish, gave the first examples of the written and literary language of Anatolian Beyliks and Ottoman period Turkish, and made great contributions to the use of the Turkish language not only as a written and literary language, but also as a scientific language.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

“Jamshid and Khurshid” written by Ahmadi in Turkish is a very valuable linguistic monument in terms of reflecting the language features, vocabulary, social and cultural life of the period in which the poet lived. The work is the first “Jamshid and Khurshid” masnavi written in Old Anatolian Turkish, the first Turkish language in Anatolia. The first and only copy of the monument was discovered by N.S. Banarli while researching the “Iskandarname” inscriptions and introduced to the world of science with the article “Ahmedi Dâsitâni Tevârih-i Dasitâni Mülük-i Ali Osman ve Cemshid ü Hurshid Mesnevisi”.

Historical and modern Turkic languages is a rich language in terms of animal names. The importance of animals in the lives of Turks, who are integrated with nature, has led to the use of animal names in almost all written and oral literary genres, including myths, fairy tales, epics, legends, poems, stories, novels, from the first literary works. This situation was not limited to written and oral literature, the Turks symbolized the animals they believed to be descended from them as “heroes” in their legends and epics, immortalized them in miniatures, motifs, statues and tombstones.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the vocabulary of “Jamshid and Khurshid”, the words denoting the concept of animals have a special weight. However, the strong influence of Arabic and Persian language is noticed in the animal names in the language of the monument. In the lexicon of the work, we come across the names of domestic animals, wild animals, and birds. In this regard, we grouped zoonyms in the language of the monument as follows:

Domestic and farm animals

Qoyun, *at*, *tavar* “davar” (sheep and goats), *estər* “qatır” (mule), *naq* “dişi dəvə” (female camel), *it* (dog), *çətük* “pişik” (cat), *gurbə* “pişik” (cat), *balıq* (fish), *tazi* “ov iti” (a hound) etc.

Qoyun u qurt bir yirdə olurdı
Geyük arslanla bile dirilürdi [1, p.364]

Nə layiq **atı** nalinə zər ü lal
Hilal olsa gerek durur anə nal [1, p.54].

Quru ot doldurdı gönləri qurıtdı
Tavar üsdinə bərkidüp yürıtdı [1, p.160].

Bir **estərdə** iki həvdəc bərabər
Nitek kim çarxda dür-ci-dü peykər [1, p.129].

Dəxi biñ **estərü** biñ əsbi-ziba
Qamunun çulları zər bəftü diba [1, p.129].

Şikayət görüp anı **naqa**
Ki anuñ sahibiydi ehii-faqa [1, b.177].

Nə olduñ xab u xurdə **it** gibi xursənd
Çətük dəxi olsa ışqın eylə dilbənd [1, p.62].

The word *davar*, which is used only once in the language of the monument, being mentioned in Mahmud Kashgari’s dictionary as in the form of *tavar*

in semantics of “*mal*”, “*davar*”, and in the form of *tavar* in semantics of “*canlı-cansız mal*” (animate-inanimate goods) it is shown that this word has been called “*tavar*” by the Oghuz. [8, v.1. p.300]. The mention of animal semantics in “*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*” indicates the semantic expansion of this lexical unit in the 11th century. This ancient lexical unit used in semantics such as 1) goods, trade item, 2) Chinese cloth [15, p.228] in the phonetic variants of *tabar* / *davar* / *tavar* / *tavar* / *twar* in Old Uyghur Turkish has been mentioned in the language of medieval Turkic monuments, in the phonovariants *davar* / *tavar* in semantics of 1) riding animal; 2) four-legged farm animal; 3) property [15, v.2, p.1025-1027]. T. Gulensoy, who writes that this word is formed from the root *tab-*, also mentions the phonovariants *doğar/dovar* in the semantics of “*mal-qara*” (cattle) [12, p. 268]. In addition, in the language of medieval Turkic monuments, *davar əri* appears in the meaning of “*çoban*” (shepherd), also in variants *davar dutmak* / *davarcılık* “*davar bəsləmək*” (to feed the cattle) [24, v.2, p.1028]. It is interesting that this word, which means “*mal-mülk*” (property) in the form of “*Ər tavarı açıq gərək*” [19, p.27] in “*Oghuzname*”, is used in the semantics of “*çoban*” (shepherd) [17, p.179] in “*Gutadgu-bilik*”. In Anatolian dialects, the meaning of “*çoban*” (shepherd) is still preserved in the form of *davarçı*. This word recorded in DTS in the semantics of “*mülk*” (property) [20, p.526] in V.V.Radlov’s dictionary [21, p.986], it is mentioned in the semantics of “*mal, mülk*” (goods, property). This word, which denotes the semantics of walking sheep, cattle, horse, etc. is related to the fact that the old Turks, who lived a nomadic life, carried their cattle along with them. This lexical unit, which being used in the semantics of “*xırdabuynuzlu mal-qara*” (shorthorn cattle) in the language of “*Jamshid and Khurshid*”, is used in the semantics of *qoyun-quzu* (sheep-lamb) in the western dialects of the Azerbaijani language, and in the semantics of *qoyun* (sheep) in the Tabriz dialect. In the Turkish Turkic dialects, it’s used as a common name given to *cow*, *ox*, *elk* and *mule* in the same phonetic variant [5, v.4, p.1378].

The lexeme *davar*, recorded in the semantics of “*qoyun, keçi, inək, at*” (sheep, goat, cow, horse) [18, p.43] in the medieval Turkmen Turkic language, has been preserved in modern Turkmen Turkic in the form of *dovar*, meaning “one who has reached a certain age, not born”. In modern Turkish Turkic, the lexeme *davar*, which preserves its functionality in the literary language as “*a common name for sheep and goats, herd of sheep and goats*”, is used in the same semantic meaning in modern Azerbaijani language as “*qoyun-keçi, xırdabuynuzlu mal-qara*” (sheep-goat, shorthorn cattle). In addition, it has preserved its functionality in our literary language in the form of *davarçı*, *davarcılıq*, *davarlı*, *davarsız*. Note that this lexical unit is also used in other Turkic languages with small phonetic differences. In Kazakh Turkic, *tovar* means “trade goods that can be bought and sold”, in Kyrgyz Turkic, *tuwar* means “Chinese cloth, red cloth”, in Kumyk Turkic, *tuwar* means “bighorn animal”, in Karakalpak Turkic, *tavar* / *tavar* means “bighorn animal”.

As it can be seen, this word, which was generally used in the semantics of “canlı-cansız mal” (animate-inanimate goods) at the beginning, expanded semantically in the Middle Ages and gained different meanings. As can be seen from the examples, this word, which is used mainly in the meaning of “xırdabuynuzlu mal-qara” (shorthorn cattle) in the modern Azerbaijani, Turkish, and Turkmen languages, has preserved the semantics of “əşya” (item), “mal” (goods) in the Kazakh and Kyrgyz languages.

The word *çätük*, which is used in the language of the monument, is mentioned in the meaning of “pişik” (cat) in “Old Turkish Dictionary” and “dişi pişik” (female cat) in EDT [20, p.145; 2, p.402], but it is not recorded in Goyturk, Uyghur, Karakhanli Turkish. This lexical unit used in Old Oghuz Turkic as *çätük* and in Kipchak Turkish as *şätük* in the meaning of “pişik” (cat) is recorded in the phonovariants *çedük / cetük / çedük / çetik* with the same semantics in the language of medieval Turkic monuments. This lexeme in the form of *çetük* has been recorded in different meanings, such as “pişik balası” (kitten) in the Sinop and Tokat dialects of Turkish Turkic, “qızılquş” (falcon) in the Chanakkale dialect, and “sürüşkən oyunu” (sliding game) [6., v.3. p.1152] in the Isparta dialect.

Wild animals

Arslan “aslan” (lion), *geyik* (deer), *fil* (elephant), *qurd* “canavar” (wolf), *gürg* “qurd, canavar” (wolf), *rubəh* “tülkü” (fox), *bəbr* “bəbir” (leopard), *şir* (lion), *pələng* (tiger), *yılan* “ılan” (snake), *vaşaq* (lynx).

Şikar içində Qaysər nagehani

Bir **arslanı** görür qəsd itmiş anı [1, p.324].

Başı **qurd** u yüzi qurd uğözi **fil**

Ayağı zəndəfil andan hazər qıl [1, p.153].

Qoyına olmuş idi **gürg** dəmsaz

İdəməz idi dürracə sitəm baz [1, p.80].

Nəbiyyüs seyf çün kim çaldı şəmşir

Öjində **rubəh** oldı **bəbr** ilə **şir** [1, p.62].

Qomadı ol tağda şir ü pələngi

Hələk iti qamusın şiri cəngi [1, p.151].

Vaşaqla pars u it ü dəxi tazi

Ki rast ola şikaruç cümlə sazı [1, p.323].

The word *arslan*, which is used 12 times in the language of “Jamshid and Khurshid”, we find in the form of *arslan* in old Uyghur, Karakhanid, Kharazim, Ottoman Turkic, *aslan* in Kipchak, *arslan/arsalan* in Mongolian, this lexical unit has been used as *arslan* in “Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk”: “Opkem kelip ogradım / Arslan layu kökrədim = Öfkem gəldi, uğradım, aslan kimi kükrədim” [8, v.1, p.125]. This word is still used today with various phonetic differences in modern Turkic languages: *aslan* in Azerbaijani, Turkish; *arislän* in Turkmen; *arslan* in Bashkir; *arislän* in Nogai, Karakalpak; *aristan* in Kazakh; *arsılan* in Teleut, *arzulän* in Tuva; *araslan* in Chuvash. In Altai Turkic, it is also used in the form of *arsıl*. It should be noted that “aslan aazi” in the Gagauz language means the name of a

flower. In Teleut, at the same time this animal is called *arsıl ayu*, but Tuvas call it in the form of *arsıl aba*. In Tuva, *aba* means “ayı” (bear). In this regard, the words “arsıl aba”, “arsıl ayu” are used in the same semantics.

Geyik “maral” (deer). “Geyik”, which is a large and beautiful animal living in mountainous forests, some breeds have large branched horns, the name given to wild animals whose meat is eaten as “elk, gazelle, mountain goat” has been recorded in “Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk” as “keyik söğüt = yabanı söyüd (wild willow)”, “keyik kişi = meymun quruluşlu insan (man with ape structure)” [10, v.3. p.168]. M. Kashgari mentions the word *geyik* in his dictionary in the semantics of the wild of everything. In our opinion, here the word “keyik kişi” is also meant as “wild person”. This lexical unit was used in Old Turkic to mean “any four-legged wild animal”, “untamed animal”. G. Clauson mentions its various forms of usage in the language of old monuments. For example, this word is mentioned in semantics as “vəhşi ov” (wild hunt), “key:k oğlı = vəhşi heyvanın balası (cub of wild animal)”, “bars key:k = bəbir və vəhşi ov heyvanı (leopard and wild hunting animal)” [9, p.755]. In “Qutadghu-bilig” it also appears in the meaning of “wild animal”: “sewiglini sevmez keyig teg kaçar / kaçığıka yapçur adakın kuçar (Onu sevən sevməz, keyik kimi ondan kaçar / Kim ki, ondan kaçar, ayağını qucar); Bu ay toldı aydı meniñ bu özüm / keyik teg-turur kılkı kestim sözüm (Aydoldu cavab verdi: Mənim özüm / Xasiyyətim keyikə bənzər, qıyası)” [9, p.29,44]. This lexeme, explained by T. Gulensoy as “mammal animal with long and branchy horns on the head of its males”, is recorded in old Kipchak texts in the meaning of “wild animal” [15, p.155]. It is used in the semantics of “mountain goat” in Oghuznama [19, p.32]. This lexical unit has been kept as a part of the expression “geyiy olmax” in the semantics of “to wander” in the Megri dialect of the Azerbaijani language: “Gədələ geyiy oldula bı yamaşlarda” [3, p.176]. This word is used in the modern Turkish language in the meaning of “mammal animal with long horns on the head of its males” [26, p. 756]. In addition, in the composition of various word combinations are used in different meanings, such as, *geyik böcəyi* (type of insect), *geyik diken* “buckthorn”, *geyikdilli* (type of plant), *geyik muhabbeti* “useless and long talk, idle talk”.

It is interesting that in the Turkmen language, one of the languages of the Oghuz group, *кейик* is used as 1) gazelle; 2) as a form of address to girls in the meaning of “dear”; 3) as an anthroponym [27, p.387].

In addition, in other Turkic languages, for example: *kiyik* in Uzbek, Nogai; *kik* in Altai, Teleut, Shor; *kayak* in Chuvash. In the Chuvash language, it is also used in the meanings of wild animal, hunting animal, deer, wild goose. In the Kyrgyz and Kazakh languages, it was replaced by the words “bull”, “deer”: “qr. бұғыны көлік етін пайдалану (using a deer as a vehicle); qaz. түндүктө жашоочу бузу (deer living in the north)” [22; 23].

Bird names

In “Jamshid and Khurshid” both the Turkic origin word *quş* (bird) and its Persian equivalent, *mürğ*, have

been used to express the general name of birds. In addition, in the monument there are enough lexical units denoting the names of different birds:

Bülbül (nightingale). This bird name of Persian origin is one of the most used bird names in the language of the monument. It's recorded in eighty-six verses: *İ bülbül dəxi dürlü sözə it saz* [1, p.117]; *Dəxi yirə nəzər qılamı bülbül* [1, p.122].

It is known that in classical literature, the nightingale is a symbol of a lover, and a rose is a symbol of a beloved. In the work, metaphorical similes are created by comparing the lover's pleas and moans with the nightingale:

Cihanı ruşən itmiş şəmsei-gül
İdər gülzar içində nalə bülbül [1, p.349].

Can u baş yolunğa qoyup bu teni-tənhayilə
Gidəram bülbül gibi uş zar u nalan əlvida [1,
p.348].

Əndəlib, the Arabic equivalent of nightingale, was also used as a fictional device to increase poetic power. The heartache and sighs of a lover separated from his beloved are described as follows:

Yüzüñjüñ gülzarını görməyəlidən i habib
Nalə idəram zar u zar ol dər ilə kim əndəlib [1,
p.282].

This lexical unit is used in modern Turkic languages with small phonetic differences. The word that preserves the same phonetic composition in the Turkic languages of the Oghuz group is used as *bulbul* in Uzbek, Kyrgyz, Kazakh and Uyghur Turkic, and as *bilbil* in Bashkir and Tatar languages.

Qumrı "turtle-dove". The name of this bird of Arabic origin means "white dove". It is recorded in the monument in just four verses:

Oturmuş gülistanda şöyle kim gül
Ötər hər şahda qumrı vü bülbül [1, p.185].

Note that this word has different usage forms in other Turkic languages. Although the Oghuz group of Turkic languages is used with minor phonetic differences such as *qumru* in Azerbaijani language, *kumru* in Turkish literary language, and *gumru* in Turkmen language, it has been replaced by the word *meşgeldik* in Gagauz language. In addition, it is used as *kumri* in Uyghur, *alatuba* in Bashkir, *miste* in Kyrgyz, *orman kepteri* in Kazakh, and *urman kügarçini* in Tatar.

Çəkavək "skylark". It is used twice in the language of the monument:

Nədir ağac bucağında çəkavək
Sabahı itsün mübarək haq təbarək [1. p.116].

G. Clauson recorded this lexeme in Ottoman Turkish in the form of çekik/çekük as "spotted little bird" [2, p.415]. M. Kashgari noted this lexeme in the form of çəkik as a "speckled bird like a sparrow". It is interesting that in the language of the medieval Turkic monuments, this word has not been used as *çəkavək*, but it has been used in the form of *çekik/çekük* in the meaning

of "field bird, skylark": "*Çekük kuşu derler bir tayrın adıdır ve turkay kuşu dahi derler (Ah.XVI.836)*" [24, v.2, p.852]. In Mugla, Denizli, and Mersin dialects of Türkiye, even today, "a field bird the size of a sparrow" is called çekik [6, c.3. p.1112]. The name of this bird, which is still used today in the form of *çekeyik* in Turkmen Turkish, in Mahtimgulu's language has been recorded in the form of as "*çəkəyik*" < *frs. çekavek*" [28, p.2277].

Əndəlib "nightingale". *İşitgil andəlibi kim nə söylər* [1, p.116].

This lexical unit, which is used as a parallel to the word *bülbül* in the language of the monument, is of Arabic origin and has been used in only six verses much less than the word *bülbül* in the language of "Jamshid and Khurshid".

Bum "owl". *Sürüp qumrıyı bumı sokdı bağa* [1, p.357]. The name of this bird of Arabic origin is recorded in four verses in the work. It should be noted that the owl is mentioned as "*kuburga*" in the "Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk" [8, c.1, s.489].

Tuti "parrot". *Var idi anda bir tuti-i pür huş* [1, p.67]; *Şəkər tuti gibi başladı sözə* [1, p.208].

This lexeme being used only twice in the form of *tuti* in "Jamshid and Khurshid" is used in a similar phonovariant in modern Turkic languages: *totu kuş* in Kyrgyz; *toti* in Kazakh; *totikuş* in Uzbek; *totikuş* in Uyghur; *tutygoş* in Bashkir; *tuty koş* in Tatar etc. In the modern Turkish literary language, *papağan* is used, and in the Gagauz language, it is used in the form of *papagal*. It should be noted that in Mahtimgulu's language, being used as *toti guş* [28, p.2283], this word is used in the modern Turkmen language in the form of *toti*.

Tavus "peacock". This lexical unit of Arabic origin, which being used both as a bird and as a poetic attribute in classical texts, has been used in the language of "Jamshid and Khurshid" for more poetic purposes in the meaning of "adorned, decorated": *Ki uş tavus dir görən kişi anı* [1, p.371]; *Bənəfşə olmuş idi pərri-i tavus* [1, p.83]. M. Kashgari writes that the peacock is called "*yun quş*" (wool bird) [8, v.1, p.331].

Dürrac "partridge". "*İdəməz idi dürracə sitəmbāz*" [1, p.80]. The name of this bird, which is of Arabic origin, is used only twice in the work. The phonovariant *dürrac* in the language of "Jamshid and Khurshid" of this word, which is used in the form of *turaç* in the language of medieval Turkic monuments, is of interest. This lexical unit is used in the modern Azerbaijani language in *turac*, and in the Turkish literary language in *turaç* phonovariant.

Şahin "falcon". This lexical unit of Persian origin, recorded in the monument, refers to a species of predatory bird: "*Uqab istədi vü şahbazı-şahin*" [1, b.3636]. The falcon has been mentioned as "*çaflı*" in "Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk" [8, v.1, p.431].

Uqab "eagle". *Uqab sunqur ilə uçardı tihu* [1, p.323]. This lexeme of Persian origin is recorded five times in the monument. It is interesting that the word *qartal*, which is the Turkish equivalent of this bird's name, has not been used in the work.

Sungur "merlin". This word of Persian origin denotes a species of bird of prey belonging to the osprey genus. It is used twice in "Jamshid and Khurshid": *Dəxi sunqur balaban ilə laçin* [1, p.323]; *Uqab sungur ilə*

uçardı tihu [1, p.80]. We find the name of this bird genus, which has two species, such as *ağ şunqar* (white merlin), *qara şunqar* (black merlin), in the Nigde dialect of Turkish Turkic, in the phonovariant *sungur*, in the semantics of “a kind of hunting bird similar to an osprey”. In old Uyghur Turkic language, *şungar* was used as the name of “real hawk” belonging to the hawk family and again has been used as a name of “*tetraçalan*” bird belonging to the hawk family. G. Clauson notes that this word was replaced by *sı>şi* in the early period and passed into the Mongolian language in the form of *şinğor/şinğor*, then it was transferred from Mongolian to Turkish with the form of *ş* [2, p.838]. The word *şunqar*, which is used as an equivalent of the lexeme *şahin* (falcon) in the 14th century Oghuz Turkic language, has been recorded in the language of the medieval Turkic monuments, at the same time has been noted in different phonetic variants such as *sungur / sunkur / sungar / suknur* [25, v.5, p.3577] in the semantics of *akdoğan* “ağ sunqur”. *Şungar*, a long-lived and predatory bird, was recorded in “*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*” as “*sonğkur: sonkur quşu*” [9, v.3, p.381]. This word is preserved in the *şonqar* phonovariant in the Borchali dialect of the Azerbaijani language, and is used as the equivalent of the bird names *laçın, toğan, quzğun, çağrı*. It is used in other Turkic languages with certain phonetic differences. For example, *şumkar* in Kyrgyz; *şunqar* in Turkish; *sunqar* in Kazakh, Karakalpak; *şinğor* in Uzbek, *şonqar* in Uyghur, *sonkor* in Altai [13, p.191-192].

Laçın “falcon”. It is recorded in the language of the monument in just one verse: *Dəxi sunqur balaban ilə laçın* [1, p.323]. In addition to the meaning of “*şahin*” (falcon) in the language of medieval Turkic monuments, this word is recorded in the semantics of “*sarp, yalçın*” [25, v.5, p.2785]. Sources mention that this word, which is widely used in phonovariants such as *laçın/laçın* in old and modern Turkic languages, is of Tokharian origin [28, p. 2280]. In the modern Turkmen language, the word *laçın* is used in the semantics of “brave” in addition to the meaning of the bird “falcon” [27, p. 430].

Note that this word is used in modern Turkic languages with small phonetic differences: *laçın* in Azerbaijani, Turkish, Tatar; *loçın* in Uzbek; *laçın* in Uyghur; *laşın* in Kazakh; *ulasın* in Bashkir, etc.

Baz “osprey”. *Həzəran olsa anə bir baz yitər* [1, p.332]. In modern Turkic languages, it is used in the form of *doğan* in Turkish, *şahin, lāçın* in Turkmen; *boz* in Uzbek etc.

Şahbaz “a kind of big and white osprey”. *Bəsi şahbaz kim soqdurdu zağa* [1, p.357]. This word is used in the modern Turkish literary language as *doğan*, and in the Turkmen language as *lāçın*. This bird name of Persian origin also acts as a legendary bird name in classical literature. We talked about this above.

Tihu “partridge”. *Ayağın boyamaş xinnaya tihu* [1, p.324]. The word *kəklik*, which is the Turkish equivalent of this bird name of Persian origin, which is used as *tihu* in “*Jamshid and Khurshid*”, has not been recorded. In our opinion, the reason why this bird, which is a bit larger than a pigeon, with gray feathers, and whose meat is eaten, is mentioned in the monument as “*ayağın boyamaşım xinnaya tihu*” because of the red freckles on its legs and beak. It should be noted that the word *tihu* is not used in modern Turkic languages today. The word *kəklik* of Turkic origin is used with various phonetic differences: *kəklik* in Azerbaijani; *keklik*

in Turkish; *kəklik* in Uzbek, Uyghur; *keklik* in Kazakh, Kyrgyz; *körtlik* in Tatar, etc. In the Gagauz language, the word *tihu* has been replaced by the word *çil* (freckle). This word is also used in the meaning of *çil toyuq* (freckled chicken).

Balaban “falcon”. *Dəxi sunqur balaban ilə laçın* [1, b.3636]. *Balaban* of Persian origin is used in just one verse. Apart from the meaning of “hunting bird” in dialects of Türkiye, *balaban/balaman/balacan* is used in different meanings such as “*big, large, fat, brave, handsome, coquettish, flirtatious*” [4, v.2, p.496]. In addition, *balaman* has been shown as “*a saz played with the breath*” [4, v.2, p.498]. This word also appears in modern Turkic languages with different semantics: *balapan* “duckling” (in Kyrgyz); *balaban* “brave” (in Gagauz); *balaban* “saz” (Uyghur); *balaban* “a simple musical instrument made of reeds and wood played with the breath; whistle, pipe” (in Azerbaijani) have been used in mentioned semantics.

Kəbutər “pigeon”. *Kəbutər gibi ağaçdan qıldı pərvaz* [1, p.252]. This bird name of Persian origin has a lexical parallel with *göyərçin* of Turkic origin in the language of classical monuments. We did not encounter the Turkic equivalent of this word, which is recorded in ten verses in the language of “*Jamshid and Khurshid*”, the word *göyərçin*. This lexical unit, formed from the word *kabud*, which means “blue”, is still used in the Uzbek literary language today as *kabutar*, and in dialects it is used as *kaptar* [11, p.113]. In the Turkmen language, *kepderi* [10, p.168] is used in the meaning of “domestic pigeon”. That is, although the lexeme *kəbutər* has become archaic for the modern Azerbaijani literary language, it has preserved its functionality in several Turkic languages. In other Turkic languages the word *göyərçin* being used in old Turkic as “*kögürçkün / kögürçün*” [15, p.114] has been used as: *gögerçin* “wild pigeon” (in Turkmen); *kögürçkön* (in Kyrgyz); *kögerşin* (in Kazakh); *kugarsin* (in Bashkir), *gögürçgün* (in Kumyk); *kögörçün* (in Altai); *kavakarçan* (in Chuvash) etc. H. Eren writes that the etymology of the word comes from the word *kök > gök* (root > sky) [10, p.168]. In our opinion, the word *göyərçin* is formed by the word *göyərmaq* (to turn blue) referring to the purple and blue colors on this bird and the suffix *-çin*.

In Turkic culture, birds have become negative or positive symbols of various values since old times. Bird names have a symbolic meaning both in Turkic mythological texts, epics and fairy tales, examples of classical literature. In the language of “*Jamshid and Khurshid*”, along with the names of legendary birds such as *anqa, simurq, humay*, there are enough bird names. Among them, the most widely used is the word “*bülbül*” recorded in eighty-six verses.

As we can see from the examples, the bird names used in the language of the monument are more Arabic and Persian in origin. Many of them are used in Turkic languages with slight phonetic differences, and some have already become passive and passed into the archaic background. In addition, the names of predatory birds in the language of the monument, such as *laçın, tər lan, şungar, qızılquş*, act as an equivalent to each other in modern Turkic languages. For example; the name of the *qızılquş* is used as *tər lan* in the Azerbaijani language, *doğan* in the Turkish language, *laçın* in the Turkmen and Uzbek languages, *duan* in the Gagauz language, *toyğon/toğan/doğan* in the Bashkir language,

şumkar in the Kyrgyz language, *tuyğın* in the Kazakh language etc.

In “Jamshid and Khurshid” the word *geyik* is used only twice: *Geyik arslanla bilə dirilürdi* [1. b.4124]; *Geyiklər otlar idi bərgi-sünbül* [1, p.324]. As can be seen from the examples, *geyik* in the monument has not been used in the meaning of “predatory, wild”, but in the semantics of a herbivorous bighorn animal “deer”.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, let's say that in the language of the 15th century Oghuz monument “Jamshid and Khurshid” it's been used many animal names of Turkic, Arabic and Persian origin. More than forty animal names have been recorded, including domestic animals, wild animals, and birds, most of which are actively used in modern Turkic languages with slight phonetic differences. Some borrowed bird names, e.g. *əndəlib*, *xüffaş*, *tihu*, *bum* etc. became archaic and remained only in the language of classical literary texts. Animal names in the language of the masnavi are mainly used as a means of fictional device to strengthen the stylistic poetics of the general content of the work and increase the expressive effect.

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